

TECHNOLOGIES FOR PROVIDING INFORMATION PROTECTION

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses information security and its necessity in the modern world. Technologies that help improve information security and prevent cyberattacks and network threats are presented and briefly described.

Keywords: devices, data, information protection, identification, authentication, authorization, access, resources, methods.

The acceleration of the globalization process all over the world, the wide spread of information technologies in all spheres of society's life made it possible to bring the level of information use by humanity to an almost unlimited level. Modern devices collect a lot of information about their users. Currently, the number of disclosures of confidential information on the Internet is increasing. In order to prevent this situation, several methods of protection are required.

Information protection is a set of activities aimed at preventing data theft, loss, falsification, falsification, unauthorized use and reproduction.

Along with information protection, the term information security is widely used in computer systems.

Information security is to ensure confidentiality, integrity and usability of information based on usage requirements.

Currently, some Internet networks require not only a password, but also a username, contact information, and biographical information from users to work on them. Such volume of information requires reliable, high-quality protection, but sometimes this is not enough. This, in turn, can cause a threat to information.

In general, threats to information can be of two types: disclosure of information or alteration of its content.

Disclosure of information means the unauthorized disclosure of the content of information to an outsider by accident or as a result of malicious actions.

If the information placed on a site on the Internet is published without the permission of its owner, or the content of the information is changed, it is a threat to information security. Of course, the user entering his data here must make sure that the site on the Internet is reliable, and only then enter his

personal data. In some cases, the threat to information is exacerbated by the fact that users do not change their default logins and passwords on time.

In general, information security provides protection of information infrastructure and networks containing confidential, private, financial and corporate information, and also affects the field of research in cybernetics, protection of mobile computers and social networks on the Internet. It allows users to protect their digital and analog data from unauthorized access, misuse, disclosure, corruption, misappropriation, inspection, recording or destruction. The concepts of identification, authentication and authorization help to ensure information security.

Identification is the process of introducing the user to the system, which uses the customer's special personal cards or his biometric features.

Privacy prevents unauthorized access to data to protect the content of personal data. It is supported by access restrictions and strong user authentication, and protects against situations where its breach may occur due to human error, as well as deliberate sharing or malicious access. For example, fingerprint, voice analysis, eyepupil facial structure and other biometric features are used.

Authentication - the correctness of the user is checked and based on it, it is determined whether or not it is possible to carry out activities in the system.

Once the user is authenticated with a unig login or password (or identification), they are granted access to confidential information.

Authorization is a set of rights granted to the user by the system.

Authorization allows the user to make copies of data, to efficiently use information resources.

Today, there are many ways to ensure information security, which together allow for strong and reliable data protection. Creating an effective information security strategy requires the use of various technologies and tools.

The proposed strategy uses a combination of the following technologies:

Brandmauer (security wall) - the level of protection applied to networks or applications. These tools allow you to filter traffic and report its data to monitoring and detection systems.

Its main task is to protect the operating system from network and hacker attacks.

The purpose of Brandmauer is to monitor and block all malicious connections and protect personal user data.

Security threat and incident management (SIEM). SIEM solutions allow you to capture and compare data from different systems. Collecting this information allows teams to more effectively identify threats and manage alerts;

Data Loss Prevention (DLP). DLP strategies include tools and techniques to protect against data loss or alteration. This includes data categorization, backup and monitoring of information exchange within and outside the local network;

Intrusion Detection System (IDS). IDS Solutions is a threat detection and inbound traffic monitoring tool rated by tools that alert you to anything that looks suspicious or malicious;

Intrusion Prevention System (IPS). IPS solutions are similar to IDS solutions and are often used together. These solutions respond to traffic identified as suspicious or malicious by blocking requests or terminating user sessions. [3]

User Behavior Analysis (UBA). UBA solutions collect information about user actions and compare their summary with key indicators. Solutions then use this database to compare against new behaviors to identify inconsistencies identified as potential threats.

Blockchain cybersecurity is a technology based on immutable transaction events. In blockchain technologies, distributed networks of users verify the authenticity of transactions and ensure that integrity is maintained. Although these technologies are not yet widely used, some companies are starting to integrate blockchain into other solutions;

Endpoint Discovery (EDR). EDR solutions enable monitoring of endpoint activity, detection of suspicious activity and automatic response to threats. These solutions are designed to improve the visibility of end devices and can be used to prevent threats from entering networks or leaking data.

Cloud security posture management (CSPM) is a set of methods and technologies that can be used to assess the security of cloud resources. These technologies enable scanning of configurations, comparison of test protections and enforcement of uniform security policies. A custom CSPM solution includes recommendations or bug fixes that you can use to improve your security posture.

This set of measures covers the wide environment of cyberspace, ensures high security in the network, cloud, within the system and other information resources most used for data exchange. This strategy works on three external layers of security: monitoring, detection and elimination of threats that can effectively prevent computer attacks, unauthorized access, data theft and introduction of viruses into the system.

